

Intervention (Brief description, who initiates, who participates?)	CAP legislation of just transition based on transformative change framework: This legislation is based on a transformative change framework that puts all sustainability dimensions on equal footing, including proper consideration of the social dimension of agriculture. Who initiates: EU Who participates: Participatory governance → definition incl. farmers, farm workers, social and environmental NGOs, who are often not included in this type of dialogues			
How would the intervention target each leverage point?:	Material More biodiversity-friendly farming practices are included in production areas, supporting biodiversity stocks	Processes Positive feedback loop as more farmers plan according to all dimensions of sustainability	Design CAP legislation and farming subsidies depend on outcomes in all sustainability dimensions	Intent Positive outcomes encouraged policy makers to dare question current paradigms
Order of occurrence:	3	2	1	4
What does the system look like after the intervention?	By incentivising farmers with more environmental subsidies, biodiversity-friendly farming is becoming more common. Linking these payments to social outcomes has changed farming strategies to accommodate green & just planning, while also being financially stable. This has had a positive effect on both biodiversity stocks on farms, but also on working conditions through diversified production and tasks. The positive outcomes on farms have encouraged the policy level to dare question current growth paradigms.			

Intervention (Brief description, who initiates, who participates?)	Trainings with migrant farm workers on biodiversity-related topics and skills as well as on their rights Farm workers have access to training that gives them a better understanding of the context of their work, teaching them not only about their rights (e.g. working hours, receiving salary in the event of illness, minimum wages, and costs for housing) but also creating possibilities for skill development in agricultural and biodiversity-related topics. The content of the biodiversity-related training would be created in cooperation with farmers and could, e.g., cover recognising pests and diseases or neophytes or a general understanding of the concept and problems of biodiversity. Who initiates: workers' unions, workers' rights organisations, regional advisory offices with financial support of the government / EU Who participates: migrant farm workers			
How would the intervention target each leverage point?:	Material Farmers are more flexible with regards to assigning their workers more complex tasks and can diversify their farming system. Workers are more involved with biodiversity-related topics and can apply their gained knowledge on their (subsistence) farms, increasing stocks .	Processes Workers do not accept illegal working conditions anymore, and good working conditions become the standard on farms to ensure finding enough workers through positive feedback loops .	Design Workers gain relevant knowledge that gives them more ownership and possibilities for action with regards to their working conditions and biodiversity.	Intent Farm workers are acknowledged for their essential contribution to strengthening biodiversity in agricultural systems.
Order of occurrence:	2	3	1	4
What does the system look like after the intervention?	Being involved in agricultural skill development gives workers more ownership with regards to their work and prepares them to work in more complex environments, e.g. with digitalisation or diversification of farming systems. Farm workers know about their rights, are therefore empowered to claim them in front of their employer, and know where to complain and seek support in case of non-compliance. Good working conditions incentivise workers to return to the same farms and provide a reliable and skilled workforce for farmers.			

Intervention	Just transition through CAP	Biodiversity trainings
Which other sectors or policies are potentially affected by the intervention?	Surplus production and export orientation of the current EU agricultural system	Knowledge on worker's rights might spread to other sectors where migrant workers are working (e.g. construction work) and might induce positive change there
Which factors, actors, or processes enable broader impact? → opportunities	Broad bottom-up support (incl. social / environmental NGOs)	Already existing structure around workers unions, worker's rights advisory services
Which factors, actors, or processes halt broader impact? → barriers	National stakeholders don't want to lose competences. Some EU decisions are difficult to implement at national level	Price pressure and the need for flexibility (volatility in order and weather events) reduces farmers' abilities and willingness to improve working conditions. High (financial) dependency on the farmer and the seasonality of the contracts could put workers in a weak position and prevent them from claiming their rights.